

Doctoral Network on Atmospheric Dust

D7.1 Dust-DN website

December 2024

Responsible Party: CYI

Project

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Consortium

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Table of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
BSC	BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE
DC	Doctoral Candidate
KIT	KARLSRUHER INSTITUT FUER TECHNOLOGIE
NOA	ETHNIKO ASTEROSKOPEIO ATHINON
PMOD WRC	SCHWEIZERISCHES FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER HOCHGEBIRGSKLIMA UND MEDIZIN IN DAVOS
TUDa	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT DARMSTADT
UÉ	UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA
UoR	THE UNIVERSITY OF READING
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

A common and efficient way to publicly present the objectives of a MSCA Doctoral Network project, like DUST-DN, is through a well-designed website. The main purpose of the DUST-DN website is to provide all the necessary information about the project, showcase its research insights, present the structure and partner consortium, promote and advertise the project's outreach activities, broaden the circle of stakeholders and ensure the project's sustainability. In addition, one of the most important aims of the implemented website is to attract talented and highly skilled students for the available PhD positions, by disseminating the call internationally, using channels targeting to academia, industry, government and the broader public.

To support this goal, the DUST-DN website, published when the Grant Agreement was signed in July 2024, has incorporated a fully functioning and easy to use online application system to collect series of resumes, academic transcripts and motivation letters from international candidates, offering a secure platform for document submission. It also provides all the necessary information related to the project's eligibility and mobility regulations. Moreover, the website is designed to evolve continuously highlighting on DCs' success stories, as well as sharing news, results and publications, project-related events and information on further career development and training opportunities.

2. DUST-DN Website

2.1. Home

The homepage of DUST-DN website, which can be found in <https://dust-dn.cyi.ac.cy/>, includes a header with the Project's logo on the left and the links menu on the right, as shown in Figure 1. The header also includes buttons for the Project's official social media on Facebook, LinkedIn, and X (formerly Twitter), placed on the right side. The homepage is organized into three horizontally auto-scrolling columns that link to the latest news pages of the project, as shown in Figure 1. Below these columns, the homepage includes two additional columns containing six descriptive informational elements about the project and its training and research goals, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Main page of the DUST-DN website

Figure 2. Description of DUST-DN's project training and research goals.

Figure 2 also shows the footer of the website, where the European flag (emblem), the funding statement in English and the grant agreement number 101168425 are clearly highlighted. The header and footer that are depicted in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively, are always visible across the entire website of the DUST-DN Project. All the links that are included in the menu on the top-right of the website header and their corresponding content, are described in the following sections.

2.2. Project Section

Under the Project section, there are four subsections: Motivation, Consortium, Key Scientific Staff, and Our Fellows, which are detailed below:

2.2.1. Motivation

The Motivation page provides a concise overview of the knowledge gaps related to atmospheric dust and its environmental, societal and economic impacts. It also outlines the strategies that the Dust Doctoral Network intends to implement to address these gaps (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The Motivation sub-section of the DUST-DN website

2.2.2. Consortium

The Consortium page provides logos and links to the webpages of the entire Network, including Leading Partners, Employing Associated Partners and Associated Partners (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The Consortium sub-section of the Project section, displaying the logos of the project's partners.

2.2.3. Key Scientific Staff

The Key Scientific Staff page (Figure 5) presents a list of all key scientific personnel involved in the DUST-DN project. It includes a short bio for each member, details of any supervisory or hosting roles within DUST-DN, and links to external academic databases for further information.

Figure 5. Webpage of the key scientific staff of the DUST-DN project.

2.2.4. Our fellows

The Our fellows page (Figure 6) will be populated with the selected Doctoral Candidates upon conclusion of the recruitment process.

Figure 6. The section of the DUST-DN website dedicated to the Doctoral Candidates, which will be populated with their profiles, research interests, and roles within the project once they are hired.

2.3. Recruitment Section

The Recruitment section consists of two subsections: Research Positions and Application Details. This section serves as the primary resource for candidates, providing comprehensive information about the application process and guidance for submitting their candidacy.

2.3.1. Research Positions

Individual Doctoral Candidate positions are presented in the Research Positions page (Figure 7). It provides links to detailed Terms of Reference for each position, as well as a link to apply during the Advisory Phase (active until 30 September 2024). Each detailed Terms of Reference also contains a link to the European Charter for researchers.

Figure 7. The Research Positions sub-section of the DUST-DN website.

2.3.2. Application Details

Details about the recruitment process, including both the Advisory and Formal phases, are provided in the Application Details page (Figure 8). This page also includes a link to the European Charter for researchers.

Application Details

Applications for Dust-DN are not anymore accepted.

We hire doctoral candidates on 17 projects (see research positions). Hereby is some general information common to all positions.

- The selected candidates will be appointed under a 36-months full-time employment contract.
- The doctoral candidates will be enrolled in a PhD programme at one or more project partner institutions, and will be included in the "Dust Doctoral Network", which involves highly prestigious research groups on this scientific topic, and which will ensure that the cohort of doctoral candidates is integrated in a dynamic and enthusiastic scientific environment.
- The doctoral candidates will learn about the consortium partners' unique facilities and research topics/methods, and will exploit these opportunities for their research. All Dust-DN doctoral candidates will work side-by-side with lead scientists at world-leading institutes.
- The doctoral candidates will (a) take responsibility for the scientific project that they are involved in, and the instruments and/or software required; (b) collect scientific knowledge through experiments and/or numerical modelling, and data analysis; (c) develop tailor-made data processing methods; (d) advance the fields of research in atmospheric dust and/or the related measurement and/or modelling techniques; (e) participate in the Dust Doctoral Network training and networking activities and (f) publish research results in scientific peer reviewed journals, and present at conferences and workshops.
- The annual gross salary is indicated in the individual job adverts, but the exact gross salary will be confirmed upon appointment (employer costs and other deductions may vary based on circumstances).
- Qualifications:** Candidates must hold a title satisfying the admission requirements for a doctoral candidate at the institution where they will be enrolled (see qualification requirements). A doctoral degree in any field is not compatible with these positions.
- Mobility:** Transnational mobility is an essential requirement of MSCA Doctoral Networks. At the time of recruitment, the candidates must not have resided or carried out their main activity (work, studies, etc.) in the host country for more than 12 months in the 3 years immediately prior to the recruitment date. Applicants must be aware that seconding periods are planned for this position as described above. International applicants are welcomed.
- Post-specific qualification requirements and preferred qualifications must be justified and demonstrated with evidence in the application (motivation letter).
- It is understood that failure to successfully continue the PhD program will result in immediate cancellation of the employment contract and the financial support provided.

Application and selection

Application advisory: A pre-screening of the candidates will be made by the Dust-DN consortium as a first step prior to the formal recruitment process. Candidates should submit a CV and motivation letter on the [Dust-DN website](#), together with their university transcripts, and the name and contact information of

Figure 8. The Application Details sub-section.

2.4. Training and Networking Section

The Training and Networking Section comprises four sub-sections: Training through Research, Network-wide Schools, Dust-DN workshops and Virtual networking.

2.4.1. Training through Research

Training through Research page (Figure 9) describes how training is combined with research activities, providing insights of the experience of being a PhD researcher working in a Doctoral Network project.

Training through Research

Training through research is a major component of a PhD project. It is the expectation of each researcher to finish their PhD in 3 years, and all efforts will be made to support them.

We emphasise learning to (a) formulate scientific questions, (b) utilise, develop, test and improve instruments, methods and/or computer codes, (c) design experiments, (d) interpret and compare scientific results, putting them in the wider context of the state-of-the-art, (e) answer scientific questions critically, framing clearly the strengths, weaknesses and limitations of their findings, and (f) formulate further lines of research useful to gain additional scientific insight.

Attendance of the most appropriate conferences and workshops will be supported.

All recruited researchers will be involved in at least one secondment to another partner institution, in most cases located in a different country, where they will be exposed to a different environment and they will be empowered into accessing complementary infrastructure, methods and mentors.

A Career Development Plan and a Research and Training Support Group (RTSG) will be established for each doctoral candidate.

Doctoral candidates will be expected to give two oral presentations at workshops, conferences or other international contexts (not counting the presentations at events within their hosting establishment, nor within the network's schools and workshops).

Part of the training will involve learning to write high quality

Figure 9. The Training through Research sub-section

2.4.2. Network-wide Schools

The Network-wide Schools page (Figure 10) provides a short description of the two planned summer/winter schools, designed to support the project's training and networking goals.

Figure 10. The Network-wide Schools sub-section

2.4.3. Dust-DN workshops

The Dust-DN workshops page (Figure 11) provides a short description of the three planned workshops, one per academic year, intended during the DUST-DN project.

Figure 11. The Dust-DN workshops sub-section

2.4.4. Virtual Networking

The Virtual Networking page (Figure 12) describes how virtual networking activities are designed to complement the other training and networking activities, providing additional opportunities for collaboration and skill development.

Figure 12. The Virtual networking sub-section.

2.5. Contact Section

The Contact page provides contact details for the Coordinator of the project.

Figure 13. Contact section